

Efficient LFSR Reseeding Technique

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Abstract:

This research introduces a novel approach to optimize LFSR reseeding in logic BIST by utilizing a new test pattern generator with the Seed Initialization Method (SIM). Unlike traditional methods which require additional memory for storing seeds this approach eliminates the need for such storage. Instead the proposed test pattern generator uses the output response of the CUT to the LFSR as a controlling signal effectively transforming the LFSR state. The design includes a net providing cell and an LFSR with reversal logic to ensure that no seeds are stored. This innovative method reduces the test sequence given to the LFSR resulting in improved efficiency compared to previous approaches. Experimental results on ISCAS circuits demonstrate that the introduced seed initialization method significantly decreases the area overhead.

Keywords: BIST, LFSR Reseeding, Seed Initialization Method, Test Sequence Generator (TSG)

I. INTRODUCTION

Efficiently testing complex circuits can be achieved through a technique known as built-in self-testing (BIST). This method involves incorporating test modules into the circuit-under-test providing a means of conducting thorough testing. Various methods have been proposed for generating test patterns such as cellular automata (CA) linear feedback shift register (LFSR) and single bit change sequence generator (SBCSG). Out of these LFSR is commonly used due to its simplicity and minimal hardware requirements. However this approach has shown to be inadequate in producing satisfactory results leading to the exploration of alternative techniques.

Weighted random pattern testing is one such method where deterministic patterns are generated using a specific methodology and then altered by weight sets. The downside of this approach is the need for memory to store all the weights as well as the fact that each deterministic pattern can result in multiple weight sets resulting in a large number of weights. Another technique known as mixed mode utilizes additional logic to transform pseudo random patterns into deterministic ones. However this increases hardware overhead as it requires additional gates. In order to address the issue of storage some researchers have proposed using the circuit response as the test patterns. However this method is limited as not all states of LFSR can be obtained. An alternative approach is the circular self-test scheme which involves adding a circular chain of logic to skip certain states and produce a specific pattern. While this can reduce area overhead it does require additional logic. Mapping logic is also used in some BIST schemes to obtain the desired patterns but this can result in increased area usage.

Another proposed BIST scheme suggests using the output of the circuit-under-test as a control signal for generating both pseudo and deterministic patterns. This can be further optimized by utilizing net sharing procedures to reduce

the number of nets required. However if a large number of nets or outputs from the circuit are used it can still result in significant area overhead. A recent paper introduced the concept of reseeding schemes which adds inversion logic to the LFSR architecture and uses outputs from the circuit-under-test to alter the LFSR states for reseeding purposes. In our proposed system we utilize a seed initialization method where the input is provided to a section of the circuit-under-test and the resulting random patterns are then used as input for the next section. This approach effectively reduces area overhead and provides efficient testing. By exploring and combining different techniques we aim to overcome the challenges and limitations faced by previous BIST schemes ultimately leading to more reliable and effective testing of complex circuits.

II. PROPOSED TEST SEQUENCE GENERATOR (TSG):

This technique utilizes both a Test Sequence Generator (TSG) and a control block. The TSG is composed of a network of cells and an LFSR implemented with XOR gates. The output of the CUT serves as input to the network of cells and depending on the control block's output the TSG will vary. The XOR gates play a crucial role in the process by serving as a reverse logic for altering the states of the LFSR. By manipulating the signals to these gates specific bits in the pattern can be toggled resulting in a new seed being generated. For instance if a 5-bit pattern is fed into the LFSR it will only produce 232 combinations before cycling back to the original pattern. However by incorporating input from the control block the continuous sequence of patterns is disrupted and a new pattern is formed based on the reversal logic. This pattern is referred to as the "next new seed." To obtain all the necessary seeds various output responses from the CUT or nets are utilized. Each distinct set of nets is known as a configuration.

Figure 1. Basic Architecture

The control unit comprises of a counter and a decoder. The counter is responsible for tracking the current pattern index while the decoder generates essential control signals to facilitate the conversion of different configurations based on the pattern index. The major benefit of this design is that all the connections from the CUT can be grouped together in a single cell allowing for efficient sharing of resources among various inputs. This is a notable improvement compared to previous designs where each input required a multiplexer to select different connections resulting in a significant increase in area usage. However this limitation is addressed in our approach by incorporating reversible logic into the LFSR.

Figure 2. proposed Test Sequence Generator

In the second figure the proposed Test Sequence Generator (TSG) is utilized. In comparison to the architecture presented in paper8 which does not utilize a multiplier its main drawback is the limitation of pre-computed seeds for generation. To address this a multiplexer can be incorporated before the flip-flop to add extra seeds. This results in a new Test Sequence Generator (TSG) with the inclusion of an extra pin seed_EN added to one input of the multiplexer. Additionally an AND gate is inserted at each output of the net providing cell and a new pin control_EN is added for controlling all the added AND gates.

An advantage of this approach is that only two additional pins are required for the new Test Sequence Generator (TSG). Its functionality is such that when both seed_EN and control_EN are set to 0 it performs pseudo-random testing. In order to execute the BIST scheme control_EN can be set to 1 and to shift in a new seed for BIST seed_EN needs to be set to 1. The output response can be obtained by setting seed_EN back to 0. However the drawback of introducing a multiplexer in this scheme is the potential increase in area overhead.

III. SEED DETERMINATION METHOD

In 2010 Wei-Cheng Lien and Kuen-Jong Lee pioneered a method for determining seeds through a specific algorithm. This algorithm utilizes a polynomial function $f(x)$ a fault list F and an input parameter L to generate a set of seeds as an output. Each seed is determined sequentially with the first step being to define a user-specified pattern with X bits and add it to the test sequence (TS). All patterns generated from this initial seed are then stored and any faults found in this sequence are eliminated. The count value is used to track the number of patterns produced from the first seed. Now let us delve into the process of pattern generation. The user-defined pattern which we will call $P1$ follows the polynomial of the linear feedback shift register (LFSR) to generate the next pattern $P2$.

This process continues until $P10$ is reached. Each of these patterns contain X bits as the user-defined pattern may consist of X bits. To improve fault coverage an X -filling process is applied and $P1$ is updated along with all the patterns generated from it. Any detected faults are discarded. The count value is crucial in this process as the X -filling is not done successively and must be incremented each time. Once the count value reaches the input parameter L the generation of random patterns is halted and a pattern is designated for the next seed. It should be noted that any pattern generated from the user-specified seed can be altered to create a new seed using the reversal logic. This modified pattern along with all subsequent patterns generated from it are removed from the TS. Additionally all X bits are modified according to the new seeds.

IV. INITIALIZATION OF SEEDS APPROACH

The previous algorithm heavily focused on generating multiple seeds resulting in the need for a larger number of nets. This ultimately leads to an increase in area overhead. To combat this issue a seed initialization method is proposed. For example a 40-bit input circuit under test (CUT) would require a 40-bit linear feedback shift register (LFSR) for random pattern generation (RPG). Instead of using a single 40-bit LFSR this algorithm suggests using five individual 8-bit LFSRs. This offers an advantage over previous methods where a 40-bit input sequence was required for the LFSR. By utilizing the Seed Initialization Method only an 8-bit input is needed for the LFSR and the random patterns generated from this can be used as input for subsequent CUTs. This approach not only reduces the required storage space but also decreases area overhead. The pseudocode for this method is provided below.

```

{* algorithm
  N      : no of seed is generated
  sequence : user defiend input
  Reseeding : LFSR reseeding generated by partitioning
  in      : clk,reset,seed sel,seed in
*}

  { * Random Generation D1,D2,D3 ..... * }
  Patterns are updated by seed generation
  LFSR_in <= ( D1(user defiends input))
  Rising edge of clk
  D2 <= Random patterns from D1
  Assume D1 to Dn generated
  output respnce get from CUT
  Repeat----->until all seeds generated
  endwhile
  
```

Figure 3. Partitioning of LFSR Inputs

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

The data displayed in Table 1 illustrates the outcomes of the proposed Test Sequence Generator on ISCAS benchmarked circuits. The empirical findings demonstrate the contrast in size between the methods used to determine and initialize the seed.

Benchmark circuit	Area	
	Seed determination algorithm	seed initialization method
C3540	2070	1554
S5378	5160	3239
S1512	3078	2693

Table 1. Comparison of area.

Benchmark Circuit	Comparison Of Area	
	GEMethod [†]	Proposed Work
C3540	1804.5	1554

Table 2. comparison of area for c3540

VI. CONCLUSION

The combination of reversed logic and seed initialization in the LFSR greatly decreases the required area for BIST implementation. Additionally it was observed that the complexity of seed generation is significantly reduced. Experimental results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed test sequence generator in terms of performance.

VII. REFERENCES

1. Jamal K, Srihari P. Analysis of test sequence generators for built-in self-test implementation. IEEE International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems; 2015 Jan. p. 1–4.
2. Saravanan S, Charaphani K, Selvakumar P. Cluster based LFSR reseeding for test data compression. Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology. 2012 Jul; 4(14):2120–5.
3. Reeb B, Wunderlich HJ. Deterministic pattern generation for weighted random pattern testing. VLSI European Design and IEEE Test Conference; 1996 Mar. p. 30–6.
4. Fagot C, Gascuel O, Girard P, Landrault C. A ring architecture strategy for BIST test pattern Generation. ATS '98. Proceedings. Seventh Asian Test Symposium, 1998; 2003 Dec. p. 418–23.
5. Kalligeros E, Kavousianos X, Bakalis D, Nikolos D. On-the-fly reseeding: a new reseeding technique for test-per-clock BIST. Journal of Electronic Testing. 2002 Jun; 18(3):315–32.
6. Saravanan S, Upadhyay HN. Effective LFSR reseeding technique for achieving reduced test pattern. Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology. 2012 Nov; 4(22):4783–6.
7. Touba NA. Circular BIST with state skipping. IEEE Transactions Very Large Scale Integration Systems. 2002 Oct; 10(5):668–72.
8. Krasniewski A, Pilarski S. Circular self-test path: a lowcost BIST technique for VLSI circuits. IEEE Transactions Computer Aided Design for Integrated Circuits and System. 1989 Jan; 8(1):46–55.
9. Lien WC, Lee KJ. A complete logic BIST technology with no storage requirement. IEEE Asian Test Symposium; 2010 Dec. p. 129–34.
10. Saravanan S, Sowmiya G, Premalatha P, Rajaram A, Sai RV. Design and analysis of scan power reduction based on liner feedback shift register reseeding. International Conference on Information and Communication Technology; 2013 Apr. p. 638–41.
11. Lien WC, Hsieh TY, Lee KJ. Routing-efficient implementation of an internal-response-based BIST architecture. Proceedings VLSI Design, Automation and Test Symposium; 2012 Apr. p. 1–4.
12. Lien WC, Lee KJ, Hsieh TY. Efficient LFSR reseeding based on internal-response feedback. Journal of Electronic Testing. 2014 Dec; 30(16):673–85